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566_Semelai

Source: Nicole Kruspe (2004). A Grammar of Semelai
Cambridge University Press

+ morpheme boundary or underspecified affixes

I. Language Profile:

Population: 2,932 (2000 D. Bradley). Ethnic population: 2,932 (2000 D. Bradley).

Region: Between Segamat (Johore) and the Pahang River. Malaysia (Peninsular)

Classification: [Austro-Asiatic](#), [Mon-Khmer](#), [Aslian](#), [South Aslian](#)

Language use: Two dialects became extinct in the early 20th century.

Loan words mostly from Malay, few from English. Generally there is little change to the form of the borrowed word, and it is treated as a Semelai word.

II. Morpheme Types

Some notes about the morphology of the language:

Affixes may be syllabic or non-syllabic consonantal units defined in terms of syllable position.

Where affixes exhibit allomorphy, this is conditioned primarily by the syllabic structure of the root and the domain of attachment: monosyllabic roots select heavy syllable prefixes, whilst disyllabic roots select either infixes or light syllable prefixes, dependent of the individual affix.

Morphological processes are strongly governed by prosody.

Two systems of affixation:

non-concatenative: takes the left edge of the prosodic head (= stressed final syllable) as domain of attachment

- morpheme templates can be partially or fully pre- or underspecified (underspecified consonant positions are filled by copying phonemic information of the base from right to left, vowel positions are filled by vowel epenthesis)
- if there is no penultimate syllable, as in the case of monosyllabic roots, a penultimate syllable is constructed to host the affix, i.e. the template cannot be infixes into the prosodic head
- in the case of disyllabic root, the penultimate syllable is reorganised in order to accommodate the affix in this position, the original onset of the root is displaced into pre-penultimate position, whilst the vowel remains in the penult

- results in prefixation in both cases

concatenative: takes either the left or right edge of the base as domain of attachment

- affixes are always syllabic and consonants are fully specified, empty vowel slots are filled by schwa epenthesis
- choice of affix allomorph is governed by the number of syllable in the base: monosyllabic roots take heavy syllable allomorphs, disyllabic roots, or bases of two or more syllables affix light syllable allomorphs

The point of similarity between these two systems is the dependence on prosody, i.e. syllabic structure, to determine the realisation of the affix.

Monosyllabic and disyllabic roots with an open penultimate syllable feed both types of morphological processes. Disyllabic roots with a closed penultimate syllable feed only concatenative processes, polysyllabic roots feed neither.

Different morphological processes for the same morphological category are governed by the weight of the penultimate syllable of the base.

There is a general though not absolute requirement that the penultimate syllable of a morphologically complex form be maximally expanded to a heavy syllable CVC

i. root

ii. preposed restricted formative

non-concatenative morphology

- preposed to the prosodic head (= final syllable)
- if the root is disyllabic, the formative is realized as infix

concatenative morphology:

- preposed to the root
- allomorphy of the prefix with respect to its weight: light syllable prefix if attached to a disyllabic root, heavy syllable prefix if attached to a monosyllabic root

iii. postposed restricted formative

concatenative morphology:

- only two suffixes, also the only morphemes starting with a V: -(?)i? 'APPL / ITER', -an 'NMZ'

iv. circumposed formative

- only one: b-...-(?)an 'collective activity'
- seems to be restricted to verbs
- ex. b<çarhũm>an 'to go down to bathe together'

v. "Clitics"

- primarily integrated at phrase level rather than word level
- syntactically driven, attach at the periphery

- two categories: “true” clitics (never stressable) and words which have the ability to cliticise (can be stressed in certain environments)
 - modify a word in relation to phrasal or configurational properties by adding information relevant to its syntactic slot
 - differ from affixes in that they are devoid of the morphological, syntactic and semantic idiosyncrasy associated with affixes
 - no allomorphy due to the prosodic structure of the root as opposed to affixes
 - do not trigger stress shift when enclitic as opposed to affixes
 - typically of the form of the minimal syllable CV, and do not require a heavy syllable template like affixes
 - always fully phonologically prespecified
 - position within the domain of the phrase is the initial constituent
 - located at the periphery of the base, either the left or right edge, peripheral to affixes
 - primarily proclitics, except pronominal enclitics =ʔen 'AUG', =hõʔ 'attention' and (=)hn(=) 'ABS' which may be either proclitic or enclitic
 - some are restricted to certain word classes, others have a broader range:
 - restricted: pronominal proclitics (V), IRR (V)
 - unrestricted: la 'agentive, causal' (N, V), mə 'REL' (attaches to the first constituent of a VP or PP)
 - ex. ki=ʔaŋkot la=kmpən hn=dak
 3A=fetch A=wife O=water
 'The wife fetched the water.'
- lukaʔ nehneh, la=ki=ckit kmpən=hn
 wound just BCS=3A=pinch.off.pieces wife=3POSS
 '(His ears were) just (covered) in wounds, because his wife had pinched bits off (them).'

III. Word

- words: $\omega \rightarrow (\sigma)^n (\sigma) \sigma$ $n \leq 2$
- δ_r – reduced syllable, e.g. syllable with reduced phonotactic possibilities for both consonants and vowels, including the characteristic underspecification for vowels associated with this position
- minimal word monosyllabic: ex. /t hi/ 'hand'
- maximal word tetrasyllabic: ex.: /k.r.wan.ceŋ/ [kə.ru.wan.ceŋ] 'coral snake sp.'

IV. Syllable

- possible syllable structures: CV, CVC
- syllabification takes place from right to left
- some URs exhibit sequences of unsyllabified consonants which are specified by vowel epenthesis in later stages
- syllabification of the UR takes place before vowel epenthesis

- Clusters:
 - no consonant cluster in the onset and coda, sequences of consonants are always heterosyllabic
 - only one heterosyllabic cluster is licensed per word and the preferred position is at the boundary of the final syllable
- phonemic contrasts of both consonants and vowels are richest in the final syllable; for consonants these contrasts are maximised in the onset of the final syllable
- inventory of coda phonemes of final syllables is smaller than the inventory of onset phonemes
- in non-final syllables potential codas are further restrained by the fact that they are in contact with adjacent segments
- only two types of codas are possible in non-final syllables and these are further restricted by the position of the syllable within the word, penultimate or prepenultimate:

i) sonorant codas : C from the following subset of sonorants /m, n, ŋ, r, l/ - may occur in non-final syllable

- most common sequence of consonants across syllable boundaries is a sequence of homorganic segments: nasal+obstruent; nasal+liquid; liquid+oral stop
- exception: no homorganic palatal sequences: palatal stops always take the alveolar nasal
- in prepenultimate syllables only homorganic nasal+stop
- ex.: /km.p ən/ 'wife'
- but also violations: /cr.pək/ 'pointed, oval shaped'
- Syllable Contact Constraints: in a sequence $C^3C^2.C^1V$; C^2 is syllabified as syllable coda $C^3VC^2.C^1V$, when:

a) $C^2 > C^1$ in sonority; or

b) C^2 and C^1 are homorganic

otherwise: C^2 is an onset: $C^3V.C^2V.C^1V$

condition: only one heterosyllabic cluster per word is allowed

ex.: //rm ɲaʔ// 'vine, sp.'

1. rm. ɲaʔ syllabification of the final syllable
2. rmV. ɲaʔ $C^2 = C^1$ in sonority. C^2 is an onset
3. rV.mV. ɲaʔ obligatory onset is required

- in relation to this:
 - consonantal infixes are all sonorous segments
 - prefixes have allomorphs ending in either an open syllable, /r/, or a conditioned nasal segment /N-/

ii) a pre-established coda, i.e. a consonant which is identical to the coda of the final of the final syllable - only licensed as a penultimate syllable coda

- driven by morphological processes: in the penultimate syllable any phoneme can be a coda provided that it is a copy of the coda of the final syllable - this is

associated with the reduplicative process referred to as coda copy (see reduplication section)

ex.: (synchronically monomorphemic, but the forms are identifiable as being complex)

/t ʔ.rẽʔ/ [taʔ.rẽʔ] 'uncivilised person'

- in a sequence //CC³CVC¹//: if C³ is identical to C¹, C³ is a coda

ex.: //klj ʔjuʔ// 'tree, sp.'

1. klj ʔ.juʔ syllabification of the final syllable

2. kljV ʔ.juʔ C³ = C¹. C³ is a coda

3. kV.IV.jV ʔ.juʔ condition: one heterosyllabic cluster per word. all remaining Cs are syllabified as onsets

Vowel Epenthesis

- used to build acceptable syllables from degenerated or unsyllabified sequences of consonants, which exist in the underlying representation
- intrinsic component of a general syllabification process
- sequences of consonants requiring epenthesis only occur at the left edge of a word, where both codas and onsets can be syllabified within the sequence
- epenthetic vowels are entirely predictable
- vowel realisation is determined by the adjacent right hand segment: the non-final open syllable vowel is determined by the onset of the adjacent syllable, and the vowel of the closed syllable is determined by the coda of the rhyme

i) 4 possible realisations of epenthetic vowels (of phonemic origin):

a) default vowel is [ə]

ex.: /d.r ɛ/ [də.rɛ] 'rattan'

b) when the onset of the final syllable is a palatal sonorant, either the glide /j/ or the nasal /ɲ/, the epenthetic vowel of the preceding syllable is realised as [i]

ex.: /s. ɲɛk/ [sɪɲɛk] 'to be sweet'

c) when the onset of the preceding syllable is the labio-velar glide /w/ the vowel of the preceding syllable is realised as [u]

ex.: /j.wəʔ/ [juwəʔ] 'to sew'

d) in words with an open penultimate syllable where the onset of the final syllable is a glottal segment, the epenthetic vowel of the penultimate syllable will be the same as that of the final syllable (nasality is not transported leftward across the syllable boundary).

ex.: /d.ʔoh/ [doʔoh] 'swidden site'

This rule never applies to prepenultimate syllables: ex. / ʔ.ʔa.reʔ/ [ʔəʔareʔ] 'lower abdomen'

ii) realisation of epenthetic vowels of morphophonemic origin

- results from the reduplication or copying of the final coda into the penultimate coda position
- 4 possible realisations (close parallel with the realisation of vowels of phonemic origin); the only differences are that in this group all members of the palatal series may determine the vowel, and the vowel and the determining phoneme always belong to the same syllable, except where the root has an open final syllable in which case the onset of the final syllable creates the conditioning environment

a) realisation as [ə]: ø > [ə] / _ C[-palatal, -glottal, -labio-velar] +

ex. /r əp/ 'to thresh' /rp-rəp/ [rəp̄.rʌp̄] 'to be threshing'

b) where the coda of the final syllable is a palatal segment, and is reduplicated as the coda of the penultimate syllable, the vowel of the penultimate syllable is realised as [i]:

[ə] > [i] / _ C[palatal] +

ex. /h ɔj/ 'to yawn' /hj-hɔj/ [hij.hɔj] 'to be yawning'

c) where the coda of the final syllable is the labio-velar glide /w/, and is reduplicated as the coda of the penultimate syllable, the vowel of the penultimate syllable is realised as [u]:

[ə] > [u] / _ C[labio-velar] +

ex. /ʔaw/ 'to stand' /ʔw-ʔaw/ [ʔuw.ʔaw] 'to be standing up'

d) where the coda of the final syllable is a glottal segment and is reduplicated as the coda of the penultimate syllable, the vowel of the penultimate syllable is realised as [a]:

[ə] > [a] / _ C[glottal] +

ex. /r ɔʔ/ 'basket' /nʔ-rɔʔ/ [naʔ.rɔʔ] 'basketful'

V. Phonotactics

i. Consonant Phonemes:

p	p ^h	b	m̥	m	ʔm				
t	t ^h	d	n̥	n	ʔn	l	ʔl	r	ʔr
c	c ^h	ɟ		ɲ	ʔɲ		ɕ	j	ʔj
k	k ^h	g	ŋ	ŋ			w		
ʔ						h			

a) Onset:

- all consonant phonemes can occur as as the onset of a monosyllabic word
- in disyllabic and polysyllabic words, the voiceless aspirated stops never occur as the onset of the final syllable except /t^h/ in two words and /k^h/ in two words
- glottalised sonorants and voiceless nasals are never attested as onsets in penultimate syllables
- in prepenultimate syllables, the inventory of onset phonemes is further reduced, permitting only voiceless and voiced stops, the fricative /s/ and the following sonorant segments /m, n, ŋ, l, r/

b) Coda

- the voiceless stops /p, t, c, k/ are unreleased in syllable final position
- in word final position, the stop may have a delayed release
- word final nasals which follow an oral vowel are prestopped by a denasalised homorganic voiced stop, i.e. Nasality is delayed until after closure
- /h/ - tends to a strong and audible realisation word and syllable finally

- in word final syllables:
 - *voiced stops
 - *aspirated stops
 - *voiceless nasals
 - *segments with glottal onset

- labio-velar glide /w/ does not occur after /i, ʊ, u, o, ɔ, ɒ/; but only before /e, ε, a, ə/
 - palatal glide /y/ does not occur after /i/ and /ε/

- penultimate syllable:
 - in simple monomorphemic disyllabic words the penult is either open with an empty coda, or in case of a heavy penult, the coda can only be filled by a sonorant phoneme /m, n, ŋ, l, r/
 - only in derived bimorphemic words phonemes licensed to occur in the final syllable coda can fill the coda slot of the penultimate syllable with an identical segment (coda copy as the result of a synchronic process or fossilised form)

- prepenultimate syllable:
 - only potential codas are the nasals /m, n, ŋ/ if followed by a heterosyllabic homorganic stop
 - ex. /kɔŋ.kɔ.lɔh/ 'nightjar'

ii. Vowels

inventory:	i	ʊ	u
	e	ə	o
	ε		ɔ
	a		ɒ

all oral vowels have nasal counterparts

- vowels appear to be longer when they occur in open final syllables and when followed by /h/; when followed by /ʔ/ they are perceptually shorter
- phonemically nasal vowels do not occur in the rhyme of syllables where the syllable onset is /ʔ/ or /g/

a) final stressed syllables

- in closed syllables no restrictions on the distribution except that phonemic nasal vowels do not follow /ʔ/ or /g/
- in open syllables: *ʊ, *nasal vowels

- /ə/ is only attested in bound morphemes
- in final open syllables of disyllabic words: *ɒ, *ʊ, *ə
- in trisyllabic words only /o, ε, ɔ, a/ are attested

b) penultimate syllable

- any oral vowel possible
- in many instances the vowel of the penult is the same as that of the final syllable
- nasal vowels are only found in expressives

c) prepenultimate syllable (any syllable to the left of the penultimate)

- the only vowel generally available is phonetic [ə] or [u] (vowel epenthesis), exceptions are proper names, expressives

VI. Phonological Processes

i. Glide Reduction

word final glides are reduced to an off-glide:

ex. /ʔw.ʔaw/ [ʔuw.ʔaʷ] 'to be standing up'

ii. Nasalization

a) Glide Nasalization

following a nasal, glides are nasalised

b) Vowel Nasalization

- nasalisation is onset driven, spreads from left to right
- when an onset is a nasal stop, the following vowel is nasalised, neutralising the contrast between oral and nasal vowels

ex. /mɔ t/ [mɔ̃t] 'eye'
 /kan εʔ/ [kanɛ̃ʔ] 'rodent, lesser gymnure'

- when the penultimate syllable onset is a nasal stop and the onset of the final syllable is a glottal segment, /ʔ / or /h/, the nasality of the onset spreads to the vowels of both syllables

ex.: /mham/ [mãhãm] 'blood'

iii. Loss of glottal plosiv

a) roots beginning with /ʔV/ lose the glottal plosiv when a prefix is attached

ex. /ʔyən/ 'to hear, listen' > par-yən (CAUS-hear) 'to inform'

b) roots with an initial glottalised sonorant lose the glottal feature when a prefix attaches

iv. Insertion of glottal plosiv

to avoid a vowel in the beginning of a final syllable. Roots which do not have a coda, select an allomorph which has a glottal stop in the onset correcting the syllable structure.

v. r-dissimilation in prefixation and infixation

geminate /r/ and /r/ in consecutive codas and monosyllabic roots of the structure /rVr/ are not tolerated

violations can arise as the result of morphological operations

solutions in the non-concatenative system:

- if the onset of the penultimate syllable is /r/, the causative infix <r> is realised as <n>
- sequence n.r is in violation of the syllable contact constraints triggering the onset of the following syllable to be realised as the prestopped allophone, this also appears when the nominalising infix <n> or affix pn- is adjacent to an onset /r/
 - that dissimilation does not occur where <r> occurs in consecutive codas as a result of coda copy

solutions in the concatenative system:

- dissimilation is not attested, the affixes have alternate forms without /r/

v. Deaspiration in prefixation and infixation

particular to onset copy. Aspirated onsets lose the feature of aspiration when copied to into the onset slot of the penultimate syllable

VII. Reduplication

- a phonologically underspecified morpheme template [CC] is affixed in penultimate syllable position to the final syllable of the root
- the underspecified segment, which may be a syllable onset or coda, derives its phonemic content by copying that of the corresponding segment of the root
- the underspecified vowel slot is filled by vowel epenthesis according to vowel realisation rules
- monosyllabic roots: requires full reduplication of the root
 - ex.: /ʦɔc/ 'to whistle'
 - prefix the template [CC]: [CC]- ʦɔc
 - onset and coda reduplicate the phonemic consonantal content of the root into the underspecified positions in the prefix: ʦc-ʦɔc
 - given that only consonants may be reduplicated, the underspecified nucleus receives phonetic content from the application of vowel realisation rules:
ʦ c-ʦɔc [ʦicʦɔc] 'to be whistling'
- disyllabic roots: the phonemic content of the penultimate syllable of the root is associated with the template – coda copy takes place into the underspecified coda position
 - ex.: catək 'to detach'
 - prefix the template [C] to the prosodic head and associate the phonemic content of the root: ca<[C]>tək
 - copy the phonemic content of the root coda into the underspecified coda position C: ca<k>tək 'to be detaching'

- coda copy may co-occur with the affixation of a partially prespecified affix like nominalising onset n- which has a morphemic template [nC]:
 - ex.: $\text{c} \text{c}$ 'to whistle' > nC- $\text{c} \text{c}$
 - coda copy reduplicates the phonemic consonantal content of the root into the underspecified position in the prefix : nC- $\text{c} \text{c}$
 - the underspecified nucleus receives phonetic content from the application of vowel realisation rules: nC- $\text{c} \text{c}$ [nic $\text{c} \text{c}$] 'act of whistling'
- borrowed Malay lexemes are fully incorporated in this system

VIII. Stress

- syllable-level phenomenon
- falls on the final syllable
- in case of words bearing affixes, stress shifts from the root to the suffix; with enclitics stress remains in the former position
- no secondary stress

IX. Loanword Phonology

Malay loans:

a) Stress Placement

- penultimate stress of Malay is replaced by the final syllable stress

b) Syllable structure

- vowel initial words of Malay are adjusted to Semelai by epenthesis of a glottal stop or glottal fricative
- Semelai retains intervocalic /h/, no longer present in standard Malay
- despite the fact that open syllables are permitted in Semelai, in Malay loans the coda is filled by a glottal segment /h/ or /ʔ/
- intervocalic clusters of homorganic nasal plus voiced stop are reduced to the nasal, despite this sequence being possible in Semelai, but not all borrowings are subject to reduction
- the sequence IV.r(V) as final and penultimate syllable is not allowed in Semelai, resolution is metathesis to rV.l
 - ex. /ru.lus/ 'straight' from Malay /lurus/
- metathesis also takes place between adjacent syllables where the offending segments are located in the onset of the penult and the coda of the final syllable, IV.w(V)r > rV.w(V)l
 - ex. /s.r.wɔl/ 'trousers' from Malay /seluar/

c) Phonemes

- Malay words ending in /ʔ/ are realised as the voiceless velar stop /k/
- /f/ is realised as /p/
- /ɣ/ is realised as /r/
- word final /ə/ in Malay is realised in Semelai as /a/ followed by the glottal plosive

English Loans:

- directly from English or via Malay
- initial consonant clusters are reanalysed as an open penultimate syllable with [ə]
- /f/ is replaced by [p]